

A Prompt Rulebook for Systematic AI-Assisted Extraction of Experimental Research Methodology: Preprint

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Abstract

This preprint introduces a *ChatGPT rulebook for systematic extraction of research methodology in experimental studies*, a structured framework developed to support a scoping review of methodological trends. The rulebook provides explicit sets of *prompts* for coding categories, decision anchors, and evidence-trace requirements for extracting methodological information from large bodies of experimental literature. By standardizing prompts and outputs, the framework trains ChatGPT to function as a consistent assistant in methodological data charting, thereby enhancing reproducibility, transparency, and efficiency in the review process. Extracted information is linked to source text with justifications, ensuring auditability and cross-coder consistency. Beyond scoping reviews, the rulebook has potential applications in other types of reviews, data analyses, and training contexts where reliable methodological interpretation is critical. This work demonstrates how structured human–AI collaboration can facilitate large-scale mapping of methodological trends across experimental sciences. The process of psychometric evaluation is still ongoing.

Keywords: Artificial Intelligence; ChatGPT; Scoping Review; Reviewing Assistant; Rulebook; Prompt Book.

I. Background

Scoping reviews are designed to map the existing evidence and provide insights into the development of research activity within a field. Unlike systematic reviews, which focus on narrowly defined questions and critical appraisal, scoping reviews emphasize charting data and synthesizing evidence across diverse studies. This approach allows researchers to identify gaps,

clarify concepts, and describe how research has been conducted within a domain.

Scoping reviews are particularly valuable in fields with heterogeneous study designs or emerging research trends, as they enable transparent mapping of methodological practices. By charting evidence at scale, scoping reviews help build structured knowledge that can inform clinical practice, research priorities, and policy development. However, reviewing extensive volumes of evidence can cause major challenges. For example, the process can become time consuming, resource intensive, and susceptible to human error or inconsistency in data extraction. These challenges become especially prominent when methodological details across hundreds or thousands of studies must be coded with precision and reproducibility.

To address such challenges, artificial intelligence (AI) can offer opportunities to assist with this process by supporting large-scale evidence extraction. ChatGPT, as a large language model, therefore, can be adapted to act as a coding assistant, providing guided and standardized outputs. Without explicit instruction, AI-generated responses risk inconsistency, variability, and interpretive drift, which can compromise the integrity of review process. To mitigate these risks, AI must be trained using highly structured prompts that constrain and regulate its outputs. A rulebook of prompts functions as a reviewing coders scaffold, ensuring that the AI assistant (i.e., ChatGPT) follows deterministic coding rules, applies consistent definitions, and produces outputs that are auditable and replicable.

The aim of this preprint is to introduce a *ChatGPT rulebook for systematic extraction of research methodology in experimental studies*, developed to support a scoping review of experimental research methodology. The rulebook provides structured prompts across sections addressing purpose, factors and levels, conditions, assignment, approach, design, and combined

sketching. Each section establishes fixed templates and decision anchors to ensure methodological data are extracted in a transparent, reproducible, and coder-consistent process. By formalizing these rules, the preprint demonstrates how human–AI collaboration can enhance the rigor and efficiency of evidence mapping in large-scale reviews.

II. Development of the rulebook

A. General instructions

The general instructions establish the foundation for how ChatGPT must apply the rulebook to ensure consistency and reproducibility in methodological data extraction (see G1-12 in Appendix). Hard Rule G.1 specifies that coding should only begin once the (purpose and) method section of a study is provided, since this section uniquely contains the necessary details for identifying experimental factors, conditions, and design. This prevents premature or speculative coding based on incomplete information.

Hard Rule G.2 requires the assistant to follow the rulebook word-for-word without modification, interpretation, or improvisation. This is critical for maintaining deterministic outputs and avoiding variability across coders or coding sessions. Similarly, Hard Rule G.3 directs careful reading of the sent sections to ensure all relevant details are captured accurately.

Hard Rules G.4 through G.11 establish a strict sequential order for coding. Each section must be completed before moving to the next, and later sections must depend entirely on the outputs of earlier ones. For example, the next section can only be coded based on the factors and conditions identified in Section One, while Section Four must be built strictly on Sections One and Three. This ordered dependency prevents logical drift and guarantees that the coding process mirrors the hierarchical structure of experimental design.

Finally, Hard Rule G.12 mandates that once the requested text is provided, the assistant must always generate the full seven-section coded output. Partial outputs, skeleton stages, or requests for confirmation are explicitly disallowed. This requirement ensures completeness, transparency, and standardization, so that every coded study follows the same structure: (1) Brief purpose, (2) Experimental factors and levels, (3) Experimental conditions, (4) Assignment classification, (5) Experimental approach classification, (6) Experimental design classification, and (7) Approach plus design sketch.

Together, the G-series of instructions guarantee that the coding process is systematic, comprehensive, and reproducible, which is essential for a scoping review that seeks to chart methodological practices across a large body of literature.

B. Cross-coder consistency

The cross-coder consistency rules (see C1-5 in Appendix) are designed to guarantee that identical sent input always produces identical output, regardless of who applies the rulebook or when. Hard Rule C.1 establishes that outputs must be structurally and linguistically uniform across coders, prohibiting variations in synonyms, formatting, or omissions. This prevents interpretive drift and ensures that data remain comparable across large-scale scoping reviews.

Hard Rule C.2 requires that each coded output end with an input anchor showing the first and last 10 words of the input used. This creates a verifiable link between the coding and the exact text source, enabling transparency and auditability.

Hard Rule C.3 specifies deterministic ordering for all coded elements. Factors must be listed in the order they first appear in the method, with levels ordered by their first appearance under each factor. Conditions must follow a strict hierarchy: Factor 1 levels first, then Factor 2 levels, and so on. This deterministic ordering eliminates ambiguity and enforces consistent outputs across coders.

Hard Rule C.4 provides tiebreaking procedures when two factors or levels appear simultaneously. In such cases, alphabetical order by the exact names must be used.

Hard Rule C.5 standardizes the labeling of condition numbers, requiring simple Arabic numerals without leading zeros (e.g., “Condition 1,” “Condition 2”) to ensure uniformity across all coded outputs.

In summary, these rules provide a rigorous framework that enforces cross-coder consistency, which is essential for reproducibility in large-scale reviews.

C. Definitions and conceptual clarifications

This section establishes the foundational terminology and coding principles that govern how experimental factors, levels, conditions, and designs must be identified (see D1-49 in Appendix). Hard Rules D.0 through D.0h introduce precise definitions (e.g., exposure block, condition block, stimulus family, natural descriptive variables) that override any conflicting author wording, ensuring consistency in interpretation. Subsequent rules (D.1–D.23) provide guidance on how to determine factors, levels, and conditions, emphasizing *parsimony* (the most parsimonious explanation of experimental factors should be applied, favoring simpler representations over complex alternatives when multiple factor–level structures are possible within the same study), unity, and correct handling of natural versus experimental variables. Rules D.25–D.30 clarify control and comparison conditions, while D.31–D.38 define experimental approaches (single-subject, between-subject, within-subject, mixed). Rules D.39–D.44 specify criteria for random versus non-random assignment, including exclusions and exceptions. Finally, rules D.45–D.49 set

explicit standards for identifying and sketching the type of experimental design.

Collectively, these rules ensure that coding is conceptually precise, reproducible, and anchored in the participant’s actual exposure during the study.

D. Randomization types definitions

This section provides explicit definitions and safeguards for identifying and classifying randomization procedures in experimental studies (see R1-10 in Appendix). The rules distinguish valid random assignment methods from non-random allocation approaches, ensuring clarity and reproducibility in coding. Random assignment is strictly defined as chance-based allocation of units to experimental conditions, with subtypes such as simple randomization, block randomization, stratified randomization, and minimization (covariate-adaptive allocation). Importantly, these rules emphasize that random assignment must not be conflated with random sampling and that procedures lacking true chance allocation (e.g., alternation or judgment-based assignment) are excluded. The rules also require the assistant to classify methods transparently, using canonical categories, and to guard against misclassification when methods are underspecified. This framework can ensure that all coding decisions about randomization are both precise and traceable.

E. Exclusion criteria

The exclusions section defines boundaries that prevent inappropriate classification of variables, stimuli, or measurement features as experimental factors or levels (see E1-15 in Appendix). These rules ensure that only manipulated exposures are coded, while measurement-only or preparatory elements are excluded. The exclusions emphasize the distinction between what participants are deliberately exposed to during the experimental phase and what is simply measured or recorded. They also set strict standards for evidence tracing, ensuring that every coding decision is justified with concise text fragments from the Method section. By following these exclusions, the assistant can maintain methodological clarity, avoid inflating factor counts, and ensure reproducibility in data extraction.

F. Naming criteria

The naming rules ensure that factors and levels are identified consistently and without misclassification (see N1 in Appendix). Hard Rule N.1a serves as a safeguard against incorrectly coding temporal labels such as baseline, probe, or prepractice as experimental factors. These labels often appear in the Method section but represent measurement phases rather than manipulated exposures. Unless the Method explicitly indicates that such phases were deliberately manipulated, they must be excluded. This prevents temporal contrasts from being mistakenly treated as independent

variables and ensures alignment with cross-referenced rules S.20a and S.20b.

G. Stepwise procedural criteria

The stepwise procedural rules define the exact workflow that ChatGPT must follow when coding experimental studies (see S1-42 in Appendix). These rules ensure that exposure blocks, factors, levels, and conditions are identified consistently, that temporal phases such as baseline or posttest are never misclassified as factors, and that condition labeling and design classification proceed in a deterministic order. The rules also establish requirements for describing participant routing, identifying control and comparison conditions, and sketching the experimental approach and design in plaintext format. Together, these steps guarantee transparency, reproducibility, and strict adherence to methodological definitions across all coded outputs.

H. Naming, symbols, and fidelity

This section specifies how factors, levels, and symbols must be represented in the coding process (see N1-3 in Appendix). The aim is to ensure that outputs remain faithful to the wording of the original Method section while also allowing for consistent handling of cases where explicit labels are not provided. By enforcing canonical naming, symbol fidelity, and derived name tagging, the rules prevent ambiguity, standardize presentation, and safeguard against coder variability. These conventions are essential for reproducibility across coders and ensure that methodological information can be traced directly back to the source text without interpretive drift.

I. Formatting and presentation

This section specifies how outputs must be formatted and presented to guarantee consistency, clarity, and reproducibility (See F0-31 in Appendix). The rules require strict use of plaintext boxes, fixed section ordering, and uniform templates, so that every coded output is identical in structure regardless of coder or session. Natural versus experimental factors must be clearly distinguished, conditions must follow a deterministic format, and classification sections must be fully standardized. These formatting and presentation requirements ensure that the extracted methodological data are transparent, auditable, and free from stylistic variability that could compromise cross-coder consistency or review integrity.

J. Input integrity and evidence trace

This section aims to make sure that all coded outputs are grounded exclusively in the Method text and remain faithful to the original source (see I1-2 in Appendix). Hard Rule I.1 requires the assistant to check whether the Method section is complete and not truncated. If critical information is missing, no inference is allowed. Instead, the assistant must still produce the full seven sections, but clearly mark the

relevant part as “insufficient information in Method” with a brief explanatory note. This facilitates transparency and prevents the assistant from filling gaps with assumptions. In addition, Hard Rule I.2 emphasizes that factor and condition details must only come from the Method section (and verbatim appendices if provided). Information from other parts of the article, such as the Introduction, Results, or Discussion, must not be used if sent to ChatGPT by mistake. This rule safeguards input integrity by ensuring that only the section designed to report experimental procedures is used for coding. Together, these rules protect the reliability and auditability of the extraction process by limiting sources to the original, relevant methodological text.

K. Mindset and guardrails

The mindset and guardrail rules ensure that ChatGPT consistently applies the rulebook with a participant-centered perspective, avoids introducing errors through inference, and maintains reproducibility in coding (see M1-15 in Appendix). Hard Rule M.1 requires approaching each study from the standpoint of a participant, identifying the exact manipulated factors and levels actually experienced during the experimental phase. Hard Rules M.2 through M.6 emphasize that only manipulated exposures should be included, excluding measurement-only variables, fillers, or un-presented stimuli. These guardrails prevent accidental inflation of factor lists or misclassification of measurement variables as experimental manipulations.

Hard Rule M.7 reinforces this principle with a concrete example, showing that if a stimulus such as words begin with /k/ was never presented in exposure, it cannot be coded as a factor even if analyzed later. Hard Rule M.8 requires a conservative approach when ambiguity arises: the assistant must insert an explicit “Ambiguity detected” line and resolve by selecting fewer factors and levels, never inferring beyond the text.

Hard Rules M.9 through M.13 formalize auditing and redundancy requirements. They mandate inclusion of self-audit statements, prohibit duplicates, and enforce strict placement of audit and ambiguity declarations. These ensure every output is traceable, consistent, and fully compliant with the rulebook. Finally, Hard Rules M.14 through M.15a provide safeguards for handling true contradictions versus missing information, and require an explicit redundancy statement placed immediately after the final condition list. Together, these rules function as a safety system, enforcing methodological rigor and preventing coder drift or interpretive variability.

L. Verification layer checklist

This checklist includes a group of rules that provide a structured verification layer to ensure that every output complies fully with the rulebook before being

released (see V1-3 in Appendix). These rules serve as a safeguard against drift, omission, or error in the coding process. The assistant must self-audit by verifying stepwise adherence to all prior Hard Rules, confirming that experimental factors, assignment decisions, and design classifications are applied correctly. Importantly, this verification must be repeated for multiple cycles to guarantee stability and reproducibility. If a discrepancy is detected at any point, the process must reset, ensuring that only outputs passing strict validation are produced. In this way, the checklist functions as a final quality-control mechanism, enforcing precision and compliance with the deterministic framework required for reproducible scoping review coding.

M. Verification of identified experimental variables

This section specifies the safeguards required to ensure that only true experimental manipulations are coded as factors and levels (see V4-8 in Appendix). Hard Rule V.4 requires the assistant to identify only exposure-defined factors and levels, meaning variables must be deliberately manipulated during the experimental phase rather than drawn from participant characteristics or post hoc measures. Hard Rules V.5 through V.5g further clarify the strict treatment of natural factors such as age, sex, diagnostic group, or language background. These must always be classified as natural descriptive variables when they describe participants themselves. They can only be reclassified as experimental factors if they define manipulated stimulus properties presented to participants, as specified in D.12c. This separation prevents misclassification and ensures that no variable is treated simultaneously as both participant-descriptive and stimulus-level.

Additional rules (V.6 through V.8) ensure that measurement-only, baseline, postexposure, filler, and preparation-only variables are excluded from factor definitions, maintaining focus on exposures that participants directly experience. Together, these safeguards enforce a rigorous boundary between manipulated and non-manipulated variables, preserving the integrity, reproducibility, and clarity of experimental coding.

N. Verification of defined experimental conditions

This section of the rulebook verifies how conditions must be identified and represented to ensure consistency and reproducibility (see V9-13 in Appendix). Each condition is defined by a unique combination of experimental factor levels, and no condition may be omitted, duplicated, or mislabeled. The rules emphasize that experimental conditions must be anchored directly in the Method text, ensuring that every listed condition corresponds to actual participant exposure. Apparatus, timing, or setting details should never be misclassified as conditions unless they are deliberately manipulated. The assistant must also determine whether control or comparison conditions exist and

explicitly justify their classification. Finally, when a condition is implied by contrast in the Method section, it must be included with a direct evidence trace. If the complementary level is not unambiguous, the assistant must mark it as “not supported.” Together, these requirements guarantee that the identification of experimental conditions is systematic, evidence-based, and free of interpretive drift.

O. Verification of identified experimental approach and design

This section of the rulebook verifies how the assistant must classify and present the experimental approach and design of a study (see V14-17 in Appendix). The rules ensure that classification strictly follows predefined definitions, avoids inference, and is consistently presented in the required format. Hard Rule V.14 establishes that the experimental approach must be classified correctly as single-subject, within-subject, between-subject, or multiple designs, based only on the conditions described in the Method section. Hard Rule V.14a provides a safeguard by clarifying the difference between true ambiguity and insufficient information: ambiguity applies only when contradictory information prevents a coherent interpretation, whereas insufficient information applies when adequate methodological details are missing. Hard Rule V.15 requires that design type be classified strictly according to the definitions of pre-experimental, quasi-experimental, or true-experimental. Hard Rule V.16 mandates that both approach and design be sketched together in a plaintext box using exact labels. Finally, Hard Rule V.17 emphasizes that assignment to conditions must be classified as random or non-random strictly based on explicit statements in the Method section, without inference. Together, these rules ensure transparency, precision, and consistency in design classification across all coded studies.

P. Verification of formatting and presentation

The rules for verification of formatting and presentation ensure that outputs generated by the assistant are delivered in a consistent, standardized structure across all trials (see V18-20 in Appendix). These rules prevent variation in order, formatting, and labeling, which is critical for consistency across the extracted data. Hard Rule V.18 enforces the exact order of sections, requiring that all seven components are presented in a fixed sequence from the brief purpose through to the approach and design sketch. This removes ambiguity and guarantees that each output can be compared directly across trials. Hard Rule V.19 restricts bold formatting to section and subsection labels only, avoiding unintended emphasis or stylistic drift within content. Hard Rule V.20 ensures that section titles remain identical across all outputs, prohibiting synonyms or variations (e.g., always “Brief purpose,” never “Purpose” or “Study aim”). Together, these rules

lock down the structure and presentation of extracted data, ensuring uniformity and cross-coder consistency in the review process.

Q. Verification of mindset and guardrail checks

The verification rules for mindset and guardrail checks ensure that the assistant applies the rulebook with the correct perspective and without introducing bias or drift (see V21-24 in Appendix). These checks function as a final safeguard against common coding errors by requiring the assistant to explicitly verify its reasoning. Hard Rule V.21 requires the assistant to adopt the perspective of the participant and focus only on what the participant directly experienced during the experimental exposure. Hard Rule V.22 ensures that non-manipulated inputs, such as measured but not manipulated stimuli, are excluded from coding. Hard Rule V.23 prevents the assistant from inferring or labeling a study as “within-subject” or “between-subject” without grounding the classification strictly in Section One outputs. Finally, Hard Rule V.24 establishes a temporal safeguard: the assistant must confirm that time-based contrasts (baseline, pre/post, follow-up) have not been misclassified as experimental factors or levels. If this explicit confirmation is missing, or if temporal contrasts are incorrectly coded as factors, the output is deemed invalid and must be regenerated. Together, these rules preserve fidelity to the study design, eliminate interpretive drift, and maintain transparency across trials.

R. Final verification

The final verification rule serves as a safeguard to ensure that all previous requirements have been fully satisfied before an output is delivered (see V25 in Appendix). It functions as the last checkpoint in the rulebook, requiring the assistant to confirm that every box in the verification checklist has been addressed. If any item cannot be ticked, the process must not continue until the error is corrected. This prevents incomplete, inconsistent, or non-compliant outputs from being released and reinforces the standard of strict adherence to the rulebook.

S. Meta-hard rules (self-audit safeguard)

The meta-hard rules establish the last safeguard to ensure that all coding outputs are fully compliant with the rulebook before they are released (see V26-34 in Appendix). These rules require ChatGPT assistant to conduct repeated self-audits against the Verification Layer checklist, ensuring that exclusions, dependencies, and formatting rules have been correctly applied. Only after successful completion of these audits can an output be delivered. By requiring 20 full consecutive verification cycles, the framework enforces rigor and prevents premature or inconsistent outputs. The meta-hard rules also mandate explicit confirmation that all relevant sections have been followed word-for-word,

that no natural or measurement-only variables are misclassified, and that formatting and section dependencies are respected. If any discrepancy is detected, the assistant must stop, correct the violation, and restart the audit process. No final output may be given unless every safeguard is satisfied, making these rules the ultimate check on transparency, reproducibility, and coder consistency.

III. Implementation guidelines

To use the rulebook to prepare ChatGPT for systematically assisting with the extraction of research methodology across experimental studies, the **ChatGPT Plus** plan should be purchased. The Plus plan is at least required because it provides access to the GPT-5 model family, which has improved reliability, longer context handling, and more consistent performance compared to the free-tier models. Free models may truncate long methodological sections or fail to follow highly structured prompts, which would compromise the consistency across trials.

After preparing ChatGPT Plus, the following steps should be followed:

- **Step 1:** A single new project should be created and named first.
- **Step 2:** Set the model on ChatGPT-5-Auto.
- **Step 3:** Then the entire rulebook should be sent as a text message within the created project. Do not provide the rulebook as a PDF, Word, or other file format, because ChatGPT treats uploaded documents as reference material rather than as governing instructions. Indeed, it can read from the file and extract content if asked, but it does not automatically internalize the entire document as binding instructions. For a rulebook where every line must be followed as a strict word-for-word, like the one developed here, sending it as a file risks ChatGPT treating it passively, as if it were an article to summarize or a source to search, rather than as governing rules to apply.
To ensure the rulebook is fully integrated into the conversational context and applied deterministically, it must be sent as plain text within the chat.
- **Step 4:** After sending the rulebook as a text message, the assistant is prepared and will request the Method section.
- **Step 5:** In response, send the purpose from the abstract and the full Method section together as plain text in a single chat message. Providing these sections separately can confuse the assistant and increase the risk of premature or incomplete outputs, since the model may attempt to generate results without having all necessary information. Copy only the textual content and exclude tables or figures and their legends and captions, as these elements are not reliably parsed and may interrupt the structured analysis. Moreover, do not provide

the requested content as a PDF, Word, or other file format.

- **Step 6:** Wait for the assistant to analyze and provide an output with all seven sections. If the analysis takes longer than about 30 seconds, stop the continuation because the process may not extend beyond this point. When the assistant is forced to continue beyond its natural response window, the generated content may become unreliable or inconsistent with the rulebook. To maintain accuracy, regenerate the response by editing and resending the requested article content. The process should begin from the first successful regeneration, ensuring that outputs remain stable and aligned with the established rules.
- **Step 7:** Review the results carefully and take attentive notes, as these records may be valuable for later reference, comparison, verification, or follow-up.
- **Step 8:** As the assistant may occasionally produce errors or inconsistencies, the article purpose and Method should be resent by editing the previously submitted text and regenerating the output five times. Repeating this process allows the mode across the five trials to be identified, providing the most stable and reliable answer.
- **Step 9:** To inquire about the provided output, you may follow up with the assistant by sending new messages in response to the generated seven-section output. If you notice any inaccuracies in the output, you can raise questions in follow-up messages to clarify whether an error has occurred. When the inaccuracy is confirmed, you may prompt the assistant to regenerate the output while considering the required corrections. This process ensures that errors are addressed transparently and that the outputs remain consistent with the rulebook.
- **Step 10:** To move to the next article, the content should not be sent as a new message. Instead, you should select *edit* on the second message, which contains the article content sent after the rulebook. The first message, which is the rulebook, must remain unchanged. This approach keeps the conversation context stable by ensuring that ChatGPT consistently applies the same rulebook while only updating the article input for analysis.
- **Step 11:** Then remove the previous article content and replace it with the new article purpose and Method sections by editing the same message. Adding new prompts for subsequent articles can introduce confusion and reduce consistency in how the assistant applies the rulebook. For this reason, each project should always contain exactly two messages: the rulebook as the first message and the article purpose and Method as the second message. Additional messages may be created only when following up on the current

article.

- **Step 12:** This cycle should be repeated in the same manner for all subsequent articles.

IV. Preliminary concurrent validity evaluation

To examine the preliminary concurrent validity of the rulebook, 20 randomly selected experimental articles from the field of Speech and Language Pathology were independently coded by the assistant and by the first author. Cohen's Kappa (κ) coefficients were computed using the `irr` and `psych` packages in R version (4.5.1) on Posit Cloud to measure the three methodological variables of interest: randomization of assignment to experimental conditions, experimental approach, and experimental design. The analyses revealed perfect agreement for both the experimental approach and design ($\kappa = 1.00, p < .001$), indicating that the rulebook produced results identical to the expert coding across all 20 applicable cases. These findings demonstrate promising concurrent validity of the assistant with expert judgments in this preliminary validation phase.

V. Future directions

To thoroughly explore the psychometric characteristics of the rulebook, including both validity and reliability, we are currently investigating its performance across multiple coders and trials in the field of Speech and Language Pathology. These evaluations are essential to determine whether the framework can produce consistent outputs, accurately reflects methodological information, and can be generalized across different domains of experimental research. Establishing reliability will show that the same inputs yield stable results, while validity testing will demonstrate that the extracted data align with the intended methodological constructs. Together, these assessments will provide evidence that the rulebook can function not only as a practical tool for guiding ChatGPT in large-scale reviews but also as a scientifically robust instrument for methodological research.

VI. Conclusion

This preprint introduced a structured ChatGPT rulebook designed to guide systematic AI-assisted extraction of methodological information in experimental studies. By formalizing deterministic coding rules, decision anchors, and formatting safeguards, the framework can enable ChatGPT to operate as a consistent assistant in scoping reviews. The rulebook provides a transparent and reproducible process for charting experimental methodology, addressing the challenges of reviewing large bodies of evidence. Future psychometric evaluation of reliability and validity will further establish its utility as both a research tool and a methodological instrument.

VII. Conflict of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

VIII. Data Availability

All rulebook materials, prompts, and supporting resources associated with this preprint are openly available on GitHub at: <https://github.com/Shahryar-Zainae/SLP-Researcher/tree/main/ChatGPT-Reviewing-Assistant>

Appendix

- **Hard Rule G.1 — Wait for Method Section:** You must wait for the user to send the Method section before applying any rules.
- **Hard Rule G.2 — Follow Rules Word-for-Word:** You must follow the provided rules exactly as written, word-for-word, without modification or interpretation.
- **Hard Rule G.3 — Read Method Section Carefully:** You must read the provided Method (and/or related design) section carefully.
- **Hard Rule G.4 — Section Two Order:** After you finish Section One, you must proceed to Section Two.
- **Hard Rule G.5 — Section Two Dependency:** Section Two must be completed strictly based on the results of Section One.
- **Hard Rule G.6 — Section Three Order:** After you finish Section Two, you must proceed to Section Three.
- **Hard Rule G.7 — Section Three Dependency:** Section Three must be completed strictly based on the outputs of Section One and Section Two.
- **Hard Rule G.8 — Section Four Order:** After you finish Section Three, you must proceed to Section Four.
- **Hard Rule G.9 — Section Four Dependency:** Section Four must be completed strictly based on the outputs of Section One and Section Three.
- **Hard Rule G.10 — Section Five Order:** After you finish Section Four, you must proceed to Section Five.
- **Hard Rule G.11 — Section Five Dependency:** Section Five must be completed strictly based on the outputs of Section One through Section Four.
- **Hard Rule G.12 — Mandatory Full Output:** Once the Method section is provided, you must always produce the complete seven-section coded output (Brief purpose, Experimental factors and their levels, Experimental conditions, Assignment classification, Experimental approach classification, Experimental design classification, Approach + design sketch) immediately, following all Hard Rules word-for-word. You must not pause to ask whether to show a skeleton stage or request confirmation from the user.
- **Hard Rule C.1 — Cross-Coder Consistency:** Given identical Method input, outputs must be identical in structure, ordering, labeling, and required explanations. Variations in synonyms, formatting, ordering, or omissions are prohibited.

- **Hard Rule C.2 — Input Anchor:** At the very end, include: “Input anchor — first 10 words: ‘[...]’; last 10 words: ‘[...]’.” This anchors the exact Method text used across coders.
- **Hard Rule C.3 — Deterministic Ordering:** Order factors by first appearance in the Method. Order levels within a factor by first appearance. Order conditions by Factor 1 levels first, then Factor 2 levels, and so on. Use Arabic numerals starting at 1 with no gaps.
- **Hard Rule C.4 — Tiebreakers:** If two factors or levels appear simultaneously, break ties alphabetically by their exact names.
- **Hard Rule C.5 — Condition Number Format:** Condition numbers must be simple Arabic numerals without leading zeros (Condition 1, Condition 2, ...).
- **Hard Rule D.0 — Foundational Terminology Guard:** You must use the following terms exactly as defined in D.0a–D.0h across all sections. Where author wording conflicts, these definitions prevail for coding.
- **Hard Rule D.0a — Exposure Block (definition):** The segment of the study in which participants directly receive manipulated stimuli, tasks, or interventions intended to test effects.
- **Hard Rule D.0b — Condition Block (definition):** The participant-facing unique arrangement of manipulated factor levels presented within an exposure block.
- **Hard Rule D.0c — Phase/stage (definition):** A phase is a temporal segment of the study (e.g., baseline, pretest, posttest, pretraining, posttraining, probe, follow-up, delayed test, immediate test). Such temporal contrasts are always measurement phases, not factors, unless participants are deliberately assigned to different amounts or schedules of exposure.
- **Hard Rule D.0d — Stimulus Family (definition):** A set of stimuli that share core properties such that manipulations can only occur within the set and cannot be crossed with stimuli from other sets.
- **Hard Rule D.0e — Routing (definition):** The structured mapping of participants into specific condition blocks or exposure sets.
- **Hard Rule D.0f — Exposure Block Clarification:** Baseline or probe activities count as exposure if participants directly experience manipulated stimuli, tasks, or interventions. Passive measurement-only activities (e.g., rating scales, surveys) never count as exposure.
- **Hard Rule D.0h — Natural Descriptive Variables (definition):** Characteristics that describe participants, stimuli, or tasks (e.g., group, age, word frequency, item length) but are not manipulated as experimental factors in exposure.
- **Hard Rule D.1 — Exposure Basis of Condition:** A condition is defined only by the factors and levels that participants are exposed to during the experimental phase.
- **Hard Rule D.2 — Constant Factors:** When defining a condition, all other relevant factors must be held constant.
- **Hard Rule D.3 — Conceptual Unity Check:** When two manipulations are always paired together in exposure (e.g., Task type and its specific syllable lengths), treat them as a single factor with compound levels.
- **Hard Rule D.4 — Construct Naming Test:** If authors consistently use one theoretical construct name across task or stimulus types, treat the manipulations as one factor with task-specific levels. If they use different construct labels, treat them as separate factors.
- **Hard Rule D.5 — Crossing Test:** If manipulations can be independently crossed on the same exposure item, treat them as different IVs. If they cannot be crossed and are always nested (e.g., certain syllable lengths exist only in one task type), collapse them into one factor with compound levels.
- **Hard Rule D.6 — Operational Unity:** If versions alter the same participant-facing property, treat them as one IV. If they alter different properties, treat them as separate IVs.
- **Hard Rule D.7 — Nesting vs. Independence:** A factor is nested when its levels apply only under specific levels of another factor and cannot be crossed with all levels of that factor during exposure. A factor is independent when its levels can be crossed with every level of other factors on the same exposure items.
- **Hard Rule D.7a — Detection Test:** You must ask: “Does every level of Factor A occur under every level of Factor B during exposure?” If yes, Factor A is independent. If no, Factor A is nested under Factor B (applies only under some levels).
- **Hard Rule D.7b — Counting Rule:** When nesting occurs, do not multiply all levels across all factors. Condition counts must include only exposure-realizable combinations. Raw and adjusted expected counts must be reported (see S.35b).
- **Hard Rule D.7c — Nesting Statement Link:** When nesting is present, you must follow S.35g and explicitly state the relationship immediately after the crossing statement using the exact format: “Nesting: Factor A is nested under Factor B (levels X only).”
- **Hard Rule D.7d — Crossing Definition:** Crossing occurs when all levels of two or more independent factors are combined with each other during exposure, producing the full product of their combinations as conditions.
- **Hard Rule D.7e — Restricted Crossing Defi-**

- dition:** Crossing is restricted when one or more expected combinations do not occur due to nesting, inseparability, or stimulus-family constraints. In such cases, only exposure-realizable combinations count as conditions.
- **Hard Rule D.7f — Crossing vs. Nesting Link:** If restricted crossing is due to nesting, you must declare the nesting relationship explicitly using the S.35g format.
 - **Hard Rule D.8 — Quick Rule of Thumb:** If authors use one construct name, treat manipulations as the same IV.
 - **Hard Rule D.9 — Independent Crossing Rule:** If manipulations can be crossed independently, treat them as different IVs.
 - **Hard Rule D.10 — Stimulus Family Rule:** If manipulations can only be instantiated within their own stimulus family (e.g., A vs. B tasks with distinct subsets), treat them as a single factor with task-specific levels rather than separate factors.
 - **Hard Rule D.11 — Example of Factor Specification:** Factor 1 (Color): red/blue for round objects, green/yellow for square objects. Factor 2 (Weight): light vs. heavy. Factor 3 (Length): short vs. long.
 - **Hard Rule D.12 — Natural Factors Not Experimental:** Natural factors such as group, age, sex, race, degree of education, residential area, disorder type, or disease type must never be considered factors, even if included as predictors in statistical models. Grouping by diagnosis or status is always a natural descriptive variable, not a manipulated factor.
 - **Hard Rule D.12a — Natural Factors Location:** If natural factors are reported in the Method, list them in a single sentence immediately after the factor box as “Natural descriptive variables (not experimental factors): ...”.
 - **Hard Rule D.12b — Stimulus-Source Manipulations:** Natural variables (e.g., diagnosis, etiology, sex, age, accent, native language, race) must always be treated as natural descriptive variables when they describe the research participants themselves. However, when recordings, images, or outputs from individuals with these characteristics are deliberately selected and presented as manipulated stimuli to other participants (e.g., listeners, raters), then the characteristic becomes a factor or level at the stimulus level. Example 1: In a therapy trial where participants are late talker vs. normal talker, language status is a natural descriptive variable. Example 2: In a speech perception study where listeners hear late talker vs. normal talker, language status is an experimental factor because it is manipulated in stimulus presentation. Example 3: In a study where listeners rate male vs. female voices, sex is an experimental factor because it defines the manipulated stimulus category.
 - **Hard Rule D.12c — Natural vs. Experimental Decision Rule:** A variable that describes participants’ own identity (e.g., late talker vs. typical talker, ASD vs. non-ASD, bilingual vs. monolingual, male vs. female, age group) must always be coded as a natural descriptive variable. Such variables cannot be treated as experimental factors unless they are deliberately used to construct stimuli that other participants are exposed to (e.g., listeners hear voices from LT vs. TT children, male vs. female talkers, clinical vs. control group recordings). Each variable must be classified in exactly one role — participant-descriptive or stimulus-level — never both simultaneously.
 - **Hard Rule D.12d — Participant vs. Stimulus Guard Clause:** “If a variable (e.g., with dysphagia vs. without dysphagia, diagnosis, sex, language background) refers to the participant’s own identity, it must be coded as a natural descriptive variable. It only becomes an experimental factor if it defines the identity of a stimulus presented to participants (e.g., listeners exposed to speech samples recorded from people with Parkinson’s Disease vs. people without Parkinson’s Disease).”
 - **Hard Rule D.12e — Group Identity Guard:** Group labels based on diagnostic, developmental, or participant status (e.g., LT vs. TT, ASD vs. non-ASD, bilingual vs. monolingual) are never experimental factors when they describe the participants themselves. They become experimental factors only if used to construct stimuli presented to other participants.
 - **Hard Rule D.13 — Nature of Natural Factors:** Natural factors are descriptive variables that exist naturally and are not manipulated by researchers. However, if researchers use natural factors to create their experimental stimuli that participants are exposed to, this means those natural variables are deliberately manipulated in stimulus presentation (e.g., listeners exposed to male vs. female voices; participants judge speech samples from people with Parkinson’s Disease vs. normal speakers), then the variable must be coded as an experimental factor at the stimulus level. Each variable must be classified in exactly one role (participant-descriptive or stimulus-level), never both simultaneously.
 - **Hard Rule D.14 — Examples of Natural Factors:** Examples of natural factors include group (e.g., people with stuttering vs. people without stuttering), age, sex, race, and disorder type.
 - **Hard Rule D.15 — Experimental Factors Definition:** Experimental factors are only those variables intentionally manipulated by the researcher to examine their effect on participants or outcomes.
 - **Hard Rule D.16 — Experimental Factors as**

Independent Variables: Experimental factors are independent variables that are deliberately altered or varied in the study.

- **Hard Rule D.17 — Examples of Experimental Factors:** Examples of experimental factors include movement, color, and pattern, if manipulated to observe their effects on participants' behavior or performance.
- **Hard Rule D.18 — Natural Factors Not Levels:** Natural factors must not be classified as levels of experimental factors. However, if researchers use natural factors to create their experimental stimuli that participants are exposed to, this means those natural variables are deliberately manipulated in stimulus presentation (e.g., listeners exposed to male vs. female voices; participants judge speech samples from people with Parkinson's Disease vs. normal speakers), then the variable must be coded as an experimental factor level at the stimulus level. Each variable must be classified in exactly one role (participant-descriptive or stimulus-level), never both simultaneously.
- **Hard Rule D.19 — Example of Natural Factors Not Levels:** If a study compares healthy vs. Parkinson's groups, these are not experimental factors but descriptive groups or natural classifications. However, if researchers use these natural factors to create their experimental stimuli that participants are exposed to, this means those natural variables are deliberately manipulated in stimulus presentation (e.g., listeners exposed to male vs. female voices; participants judge speech samples from people with Parkinson's Disease vs. normal speakers), then the variable must be coded as an experimental factor at the stimulus level. Each variable must be classified in exactly one role (participant-descriptive or stimulus-level), never both simultaneously.
- **Hard Rule D.20 — Factor Definition Clarification:** A factor must only be a manipulated variable intended to test its effect.
- **Hard Rule D.21 — Stimulus Clarification:** A stimulus is the presentation item or content given to participants, which may vary but does not constitute a factor unless its properties (e.g., color, pattern, movement) are directly manipulated by the researcher.
- **Hard Rule D.22 — Preparation Materials Not Factors:** If a stimulus version is created or used only during materials preparation and is not intentionally presented to participants during the exposure block as part of a manipulation, it must not be considered a factor level.
- **Hard Rule D.23 — Factor Level Existence:** A factor level exists only if the researcher deliberately includes it in the exposure phase to test its effect.
- **Hard Rule D.23a — Parsimony Override:**

When more than one valid factorization of exposures is possible, coders must adopt the solution with the fewest factors, provided no directly manipulated exposure dimension is omitted. Collapsing is mandatory if it avoids introducing redundant or nested factors that could instead be represented as compound levels.

- **Hard Rule D.23b — Task Type Collapsing:** Do not code "Task type" (e.g., A vs. B versions of the same task) as a separate factor if its differences are fully explained by other factors such as syllable length or nonword identity. In such cases, encode task type implicitly by nesting/compounding levels within those other factors.
- **Hard Rule D.24 — Example of Factor and Levels:** Factor 1: Color — red, green Factor 2: Shape — circle, square, triangle
- **Hard Rule D.25 — Control Condition Definition:** A control condition is one in which participants do not receive the experimental condition, treatment, or intervention. It serves as a baseline for comparing the effects of the experimental condition.
- **Hard Rule D.26 — Control Condition Example:** If participants with aphasia receive MIT treatment in one condition, while in another condition participants do not receive any experimental treatment, the latter is the control condition.
- **Hard Rule D.27 — Comparison Condition Definition:** A comparison condition is one in which participants receive a different experimental condition, treatment, alternative intervention, or a meaningful variation without being completely untreated like a control condition.
- **Hard Rule D.28 — Comparison Condition Example:** If researchers test the effect of light color on anxiety using blue light in one condition and red light in another, these are comparison conditions.
- **Hard Rule D.29 — Coexistence of Control and Comparison Conditions:** Studies may include both control and comparison conditions.
- **Hard Rule D.30 — Mixed Example of Control and Comparison:** If a study tests the effect of ice cream on teeth with three conditions — no ice cream (control), sweetened ice cream, and sugar-free ice cream (comparison conditions) — then one control condition and two comparison conditions exist.
- **Hard Rule D.30a — Condition Count and Experimental Approach:** A study with only one condition is classified as pre-experimental. If more than one condition is identified, the study cannot be classified as pre-experimental under any circumstance, even if no control condition exists. Such studies must instead be classified as quasi-experimental (if assignment is not random) or true-experimental (if assignment is random).

- **Hard Rule D.31 — Single-Subject Core Criterion:** A single-subject or single-case design uses a small number of participants over time; ‘small’ is approximately 15 or fewer and is the key feature distinguishing it from within-subject design. For classification purposes, all single-subject designs are treated as pre-experimental regardless of randomization or control features (see D.44a).
- **Hard Rule D.32 — Single-Subject Named Designs:** Classify as single-subject if the study explicitly uses AB, ABA, ABAB, Multiple Baseline, Changing Criterion, Alternating Treatments (Multi-Element), or Multiple Treatment designs. For classification purposes, all such single-subject designs are pre-experimental (see D.31, D.44a). Do not elevate to quasi- or true-experimental.
- **Hard Rule D.33 — Between-Subject Definition:** In a between-subject approach, each participant is assigned to only one experimental condition; no individual is exposed to more than one condition.
- **Hard Rule D.34 — Between-Subject Example:** If conditions are “red light” vs. “green light,” each participant experiences only one of these conditions.
- **Hard Rule D.35 — Within-Subject Definition:** In a within-subject approach, each participant is assigned to all experimental conditions; all people experience all conditions.
- **Hard Rule D.36 — Within-Subject Example:** If conditions are car A, car B, car C, and car D, all participants experience all four conditions.
- **Hard Rule D.37 — Multiple Designs (Mixed) Definition:** If a study combines within-subject and between-subject approaches, classify it as multiple designs; participants are exposed to only a specific set (subset) of conditions, and within each assigned set they experience all included conditions.
- **Hard Rule D.38 — Multiple Designs Examples:** • Four conditions (1–4): Group 1 completes 1–2; Group 2 completes 3–4. • Six conditions (A–F): Group 1 completes A–B; Group 2 completes C–D; Group 3 completes E–F. • Eight conditions (1–8): Group 1 completes 1–4; Group 2 completes 5–8.
- **Hard Rule D.39 — Definition of Random Assignment (primary definition):** A study must be classified as random assignment if the Method explicitly states participants were assigned to conditions using a randomization procedure (e.g., “randomly assigned,” “random allocation,” “block-randomized,” “stratified randomization,” or “minimization with random element”), regardless of whether the specific subtype is fully detailed.
- **Hard Rule D.40 — Non-Random Assignment Definition:** Non-random assignment means participants were allocated to condition(s) by systematic, purposive, or convenience-based rules (e.g., odd/even IDs, counterbalanced, classroom membership, clinical status, matching by age/sex).
- **Hard Rule D.41 — No Inference:** If the Method does not contain the word “random” (or any form, such as “randomly assigned,” “randomization,” “block-randomized,” “stratified randomization”), then classify as non-random. If the Method does contain such a term and it clearly applies to assignment to conditions (not random sampling, random slopes, random intercepts, pseudorandom, etc.), classify as random assignment even if the procedural details (e.g., concealment, sequence generation) are not fully specified.
- **Hard Rule D.42 — Natural Factors vs. Assignment:** Group membership based on natural factors (e.g., without aphasia vs. with aphasia, male vs. female) is not random assignment. These are descriptive groups, not randomized allocations.
- **Hard Rule D.43 — Random Keyword Check:** (cross-reference: see D.39–D.44).
- **Hard Rule D.44 — Exclusions From Random Assignment:** The following terms must never be considered evidence of random assignment: “pseudorandom,” “pseudo-random,” “pseudorandomization,” “pseudo-randomization,” “semirandomized,” “semi-randomized,” “random effect,” “random intercept,” “random slope,” “random sampling,” or “counterbalancing.” However, terms such as “randomly assigned,” “block-randomized,” “stratified randomization,” or “minimization with random element” must be treated as valid evidence of random assignment, because they refer to recognized allocation procedures.
- **Hard Rule D.44a — Random Assignment in Single-Subject Designs:** For classification purposes, all single-subject designs are treated as pre-experimental, regardless of whether randomization of phases or onset is used. Random assignment in the group-design sense (allocation of participants to different conditions) does not apply to single-subject studies. Do not elevate a single-subject design to quasi- or true experimental status based on randomization features.
- **Hard Rule D.44b — Random Assignment in Between-Subject Designs:** In between-subject designs, random assignment refers only to whether participants were allocated to different condition blocks by chance. Each participant experiences only one condition; randomization of stimulus order within that condition does not count as random assignment.
- **Hard Rule D.44c — Random Assignment in Within-Subject Designs:** In within-subject designs, random assignment refers to whether the order of exposure to all conditions was random-

ized. Because each participant experiences every condition, only order randomization qualifies as evidence of random assignment. Randomization of stimulus order within a single condition does not qualify.

- **Hard Rule D.44d — Random Assignment in Multiple-Designs (Mixed) Approaches:** In multiple-designs approaches, random assignment can occur in either of two ways: (1) participants are randomly assigned to subsets of conditions, or (2) the order of conditions within each subset is randomized. Evidence of either pathway is sufficient for classifying the study as random assignment.
- **Hard Rule D.44e — Stimulus Order vs. Condition Order:** Randomization of trial-level or stimulus presentation order within a condition is not evidence of random assignment. Random assignment always requires randomization at the condition or condition-order level as specified in D.44a–D.44c.
- **Hard Rule D.44f — Trial-Level Randomization Exception:** Do not normally treat randomized trial or stimulus order as random assignment. Exception: If the randomized trial order itself is the manipulated factor (e.g., for example, studies where the exposure condition is defined by a randomized sequence of items such as words in a learning task or light color flashes in a perception task), then classify as random assignment. This is rare. In all other cases, randomization of stimulus order for counterbalancing or nuisance control does not qualify.
- **Hard Rule D.45 — Experimental Design Identification:** You must determine the experimental design strictly and only based on the provided definitions of pre-experimental, quasi-experimental, and true-experimental designs.
- **Hard Rule D.46 — Pre-Experimental Definition:** Pre-experimental design must be classified only when the study includes exactly one condition. If more than one condition exists, the study cannot be classified as pre-experimental. Instead, classification must proceed as quasi-experimental (if assignment is not random) or true-experimental (if assignment is random). Applies to any approach (single-subject, between-subject, or within-subject).
- **Hard Rule D.47 — Quasi-Experimental Definition:** Quasi-experimental design must be classified when there is at least one control or comparison condition, but assignment of participants to experimental condition is not random. Only applies to the between-subject, within-subject, or multiple designs approaches.
- **Hard Rule D.48 — True-Experimental Definition:** True-experimental design must be classified when there is at least one control or comparison

condition, and assignment of participants to experimental condition is random. Only applies to the between-subject, within-subject, or multiple designs approaches.

- **Hard Rule R.1 — Definition of Random Assignment:** Random assignment is any allocation procedure in which units are assigned to conditions purely by chance, with each unit having a known nonzero probability of assignment to each condition.
- **Hard Rule R.2 — Non-Random Methods Exclusion:** Procedures such as date of birth, date of presentation, case record number, alternation, haphazard allocation, or judgment-based assignment must never be classified as random assignment. These are non-random allocation methods and must be excluded.
- **Hard Rule R.3 — Integrity Requirement:** For any allocation method to qualify as random assignment, it must satisfy both: Generation of an unpredictable random sequence (e.g., coin toss, random numbers, computer generator). Proper concealment of the sequence until assignment occurs (e.g., opaque sealed envelopes, central randomization, coded bottles). Where concealment is not reported, assume not described rather than not performed; do not downgrade to non-random solely for lack of concealment detail.
- **Hard Rule R.4 — Simple Randomization:** Every unit has an independent and equal probability of assignment to each condition. Examples: coin toss, dice roll, shuffled cards, random number tables, computer random number generator.
- **Hard Rule R.5 — Block Randomization (Restricted Randomization):** Ensures balance in the number of participants assigned to each group at regular intervals by using fixed block sizes (e.g., 4, 6). Within each block, all treatment allocations occur in equal numbers in randomized order.
- **Hard Rule R.6 — Stratified Randomization:** Participants are divided into strata (subgroups) based on prognostic factors, and randomization occurs separately within each stratum. Stratification must always be paired with a randomization method (often block randomization).
- **Hard Rule R.7 — Minimization (Covariate-Adaptive Allocation):** Assignment of each new participant is based on minimizing covariate imbalance across treatment conditions. First participant is assigned randomly; subsequent assignments are based on covariate balancing. Not fully random — a random element (e.g., tie-breaker or probability-weighted assignment) should be added. Always label as “Minimization (Covariate-Adaptive), not fully random.”
- **Hard Rule R.8 — Random Assignment vs. Random Sampling:** Random assignment = chance-based allocation of units to conditions.

Random sampling = chance-based selection of units from a population. Never conflate the two.

- **Hard Rule R.9 — Classification Template:** When classifying randomization in coding outputs, all randomization procedures must be labeled using one of the following canonical categories: Simple Randomization Block Randomization Stratified Randomization Minimization (Covariate-Adaptive)
- **Hard Rule R.10 — Guard Against Misclassification:** If the Method says only that “participants were randomized to conditions” (or equivalent wording) without specifying the subtype, classify as Random assignment — subtype unspecified (do not downgrade to non-random). If the Method names a subtype (e.g., “block-randomized to conditions,” “stratified randomization to conditions”), classify it under that subtype directly, even if procedural details are absent. Only when the Method provides no mention of randomization to conditions at all must you classify as Non-random assignment.
- **Hard Rule E.1 — Stimulus Not Presented:** If a stimulus or category is not presented during exposure, it is not a level.
- **Hard Rule E.2 — Analysis-Only Variables:** Variables that exist only in baseline, prepractice, probe, postexposure, or analysis phases are not factors. Exclude them unless the Method explicitly defines them as manipulated exposure.
- **Hard Rule E.3 — Absence of Exposure:** Absence of exposure is not a level unless absence/presence is deliberately manipulated during the exposure block.
- **Hard Rule E.4 — Stimulus vs. Factor Clarification:** Stimuli such as objects, images, words, or sounds are not factors unless the stimulus type itself is deliberately manipulated to examine its effect.
- **Hard Rule E.5 — Objects Without Manipulated Properties:** If different objects are used but the same properties (e.g., color, movement) are tested across them, the objects are not factors.
- **Hard Rule E.6 — Stimulus Factor Creation:** A stimulus factor exists only when different versions of a stimulus (e.g., shapes, colors, sounds) are intentionally manipulated to test their effect on the outcome.
- **Hard Rule E.7 — Factor Definition:** A factor is a manipulated variable designed to examine its effect on participants, such as color, pattern, or movement.
- **Hard Rule E.8 — Measurement Regions Not Factors:** If a study records physiological signals from multiple anatomical or sensor regions (e.g., pharyngeal regions, EEG channels, EMG muscles, brain ROIs), these are measurement dimensions only. They must never be treated as experimental factors or levels unless participants are deliberately assigned to experience different regions as part of the exposure manipulation.
- **Hard Rule E.9 — Stimulus Definition:** A stimulus is a presentation item or content given to the participant, which may vary but is not itself a factor unless its properties are directly manipulated.
- **Hard Rule E.10 — Distinction Rule:** The difference between an experimental factor and a presentation stimulus must be maintained: experimental factors are deliberately manipulated variables, while stimuli are presentation items unless their properties are manipulated.
- **Hard Rule E.11 — Evidence Trace Length:** When quoting for evidence trace, extract the shortest text that demonstrates the factor, level, or assignment decision. Prefer ≤ 20 words, but if a longer fragment is needed to preserve clarity or context, allow up to 30 words with [brackets] to trim irrelevant text. Do not clip so tightly that qualifiers are lost. When using implied complements per V.13, the quote may reference the clause that establishes the contrast (≤ 20 words; ≤ 30 if needed to retain the qualifier).
- **Hard Rule E.12 — Evidence Trace for Control/Comparison:** When claiming a condition is control or comparison, include a ≤ 20 -word quote fragment from the Method that shows why.
- **Hard Rule E.13 — Negative Evidence Trace:** When marking “[not supported]” in assignment/design classification boxes, include a short quote fragment (≤ 20 words) that shows why evidence was absent or insufficient (e.g., “no mention of assignment procedure”).
- **Hard Rule E.14 — Exposure Evidence Trace:** When identifying exposure blocks and excluded phases, cite ≤ 20 -word Method fragments that support inclusion or exclusion.
- **Hard Rule E.15 — Probes Not Factors:** Probe lists, probe word sets, or probe tasks used only for outcome measurement must never be classified as experimental factors or levels. They are measurement-only variables. Only variables that deliberately manipulate participant exposure during the intervention (e.g., treatment program, feedback type, dosage) qualify as experimental factors.
- **Hard Rule N.1a — Factor Naming Guard:** If a researcher labels baseline, probe, or prepractice as a “phase,” do not treat it as a factor unless explicitly manipulated. Exclude by default. Cross-reference S.20a and S.20b.
- **Hard Rule S.1 — Identify Exposure Block:** You must first identify the exposure block(s).
- **Hard Rule S.1a — Exposure Block Statement:** Baseline, probe, and prepractice sessions are measurement phases only. They must never be treated

- as factors or conditions, even if participants engage with stimuli, unless the Method explicitly states that these are manipulated exposure conditions.
- **Hard Rule S.6 — Exposure-Only Factors and Levels:** When defining factors and levels, use only content that participants actually experienced during the exposure block(s). If a predictor is based on pre-existing participant characteristics (e.g., diagnostic group), do not classify it as an experimental factor even if analyzed; list it only under natural descriptive variables. Reminder: diagnostic or developmental group membership is not exposure. If no stimulus or task changes as a result of group identity, do not code it as a factor.
 - **Hard Rule S.7 — Exclude Non-Exposure Variables:** Ignore variables and items that appear only in baseline, postexposure, or analysis models.
 - **Hard Rule S.8 — Exclude Measurement-Only Variables:** Do not promote variables from measurement-only phases into factors.
 - **Hard Rule S.9 — Define Factor:** A factor may represent either (a) a single manipulated dimension (e.g., color), or (b) a nested compound manipulation (e.g., Task × Syllable Length) when the levels cannot be separated in exposure.
 - **Hard Rule S.10 — Define Level:** A level may be (a) a pure manipulation (e.g., “red”), or (b) a compound level when two or more manipulations are inseparably paired in exposure and cannot be independently crossed. In such cases, all inseparable manipulations must be collapsed into a single factor with compound levels (e.g., “P-words — 1 syllable,” “P-words — 2 syllables,” “P-words — 3 syllables,” “T-words — 1 syllable,” “T-words — 2 syllables,” “T-words — 3 syllables”).
 - **Hard Rule S.10a — Collapsing Justification:** Collapse inseparable or nested manipulations into single compound factors whenever possible. Parsimony takes precedence: if exposures can be equivalently represented by fewer factors, coders must collapse into the smallest factor set that fully captures all manipulated stimuli.
 - **Hard Rule S.11 — Exclude Analysis-Only Variables:** Do not treat variables that appear only in baseline, postexposure, or in the statistical model as factors.
 - **Hard Rule S.11a — Stimulus–Factor Distinction Statement:** For any prominent stimulus dimension excluded as a factor, add a one-sentence rationale referencing E.4/E.10.
 - **Hard Rule S.12 — Exclude Non-Exposure Items:** Do not treat items never presented during exposure as factors.
 - **Hard Rule S.13 — Exclude Filler/Familiarization:** Do not treat filler or familiarization items not intended to produce an effect as factors.
 - **Hard Rule S.14 — Nonexposure is Not a Level:** Do not treat nonexposure as a level unless the design deliberately contrasts different exposure contents during the exposure block(s).
 - **Hard Rule S.15 — Describe Participant Distribution:** You must describe exactly how participants were assigned or exposed to the arrangement of factors and levels during the exposure block(s).
 - **Hard Rule S.15a — Participant Distribution Template:** Present participant exposure routing in one compact line: “Routing: participants → [grouping rule if any] → exposure to [Factor 1 levels per group]; all participants [or subset] experienced [Factor 2 levels ...].”
 - **Hard Rule S.16 — Example Uniform Exposure:** If all participants receive the same exposure, state it directly (e.g., “All participants listened to extended-VOT /p/ words”).
 - **Hard Rule S.17 — Example Grouped Exposure:** If participants are split into groups, state the group-specific exposures (e.g., “Group 1 saw Y while Group 2 saw Z”).
 - **Hard Rule S.18 — No Design Labels:** Do not label designs using terms such as “within-subjects” or “between-subjects.”
 - **Hard Rule S.19 — No Baseline/Postexposure Groups:** Do not create groups or conditions from baseline or postexposure measurement categories.
 - **Hard Rule S.19a — Temporal Guard Clause:** Before listing factors, coder must explicitly check for temporal contrasts (e.g. baseline, before/after, pre/post, immediate/delayed, follow-up, longitudinal timepoints). These are *phases only* and cannot be coded as factors or levels unless exposure amount or schedule is deliberately manipulated between participants. If detected, coder must write: “Temporal contrast detected — excluded per S.20a/S.20c/S.20d. Treated as phase only.”
 - **Hard Rule S.20 — Time Not a Factor by Default:** If the only difference is time (e.g., baseline → exposure → posttest), time is not a factor. Any temporal contrast (e.g., baseline, pre/post, before/after, follow-up, immediate/delayed) is a measurement phase only.
 - **Hard Rule S.20a — Baseline Guard Clause:** Baseline sessions are for measurement, not manipulation. Do not classify them as exposure conditions.
 - **Hard Rule S.20b — Phases Not Levels:** Temporal contrasts (e.g., baseline, pre/post, before/after, follow-up, immediate vs delayed) must never be coded as levels unless time itself has been deliberately manipulated as a factor.
 - **Hard Rule S.20c — Universal Safeguard:** If all participants experience each temporal stage (e.g., baseline, pre, post, follow-up), those stages are phases only. Coders must classify them as

phases and not as manipulated factors, unless explicit assignment to different exposure durations/schedules is described.

- **Hard Rule S.21 — Deliberate Time Manipulation:** Time is a factor only if participants are deliberately assigned to different amounts or schedules of exposure (e.g., 10 hr vs. 5 hr training, immediate vs. delayed). Pre/post measurement comparisons of the same exposure sequence do not count as factors. These are phases for outcome assessment and must be excluded from both factors and levels.
- **Hard Rule S.21a — Sequence Guard for Time:** Even when time is mentioned, if all participants pass through the same sequence (e.g., baseline → pretest → training → posttest → follow-up), these contrasts are phases only. They must not be treated as factors or levels unless explicit between-participant assignment to different exposure schedules is described.
- **Hard Rule S.22 — Non-Exposure Periods:** A non-exposure period is not a factor unless it is deliberately manipulated, in which case it becomes a level alongside the exposure level(s).
- **Hard Rule S.23 — Condition Block Definition:** Each unique combination of factor levels must be treated as one condition block.
- **Hard Rule S.24 — Condition Labeling:** Each condition block must include a label in the format: Condition X — [Factor 1 Level] + [Factor 2 Level].
- **Hard Rule S.25 — Condition Exposure Details:** For each condition block, list the levels participants were exposed to in the format: Factor 1: [level description] Factor 2: [level description].
- **Hard Rule S.26 — Exclude Unrelated Details:** Do not include apparatus, timing, or setting unless they are part of the manipulation itself.
- **Hard Rule S.27 — Relabel Condition Names:** Re-label author-given condition names if they do not conform to this definition of a condition.
- **Hard Rule S.28 — Identify Control or Comparison Conditions:** At Step 7, determine whether the study includes a control condition, a comparison condition, or neither based strictly on the complete list of conditions identified in Section One. Do not base this decision solely on the nature of the factors; instead, examine whether any condition represents (a) absence of the experimental manipulation (control) or (b) a different experimental arrangement serving as a meaningful comparator (comparison).
- **Hard Rule S.28a — Guard Clause:** Never use statements about “all conditions being versions of the same factor” as the sole basis for concluding “no control or comparison conditions.” The decision must explicitly refer to the condition blocks from Section One and how they relate to each other in terms of presence/absence or type of manipulation.
- **Hard Rule S.28b — Explicit Control/Comparison Declaration:** If a condition matches the definitions in D.25–D.28, you must explicitly label it as control or comparison in the classification step, even if it could also be described as “just another factor level.”
- **Hard Rule S.28c — Evidence Integration:** When declaring “yes” or “no” for control/comparison conditions, the explanation sentence must include a ≤ 20 -word quote fragment from the Method to anchor the decision.
- **Hard Rule S.29 — No Control/Comparison:** If multiple conditions exist but none qualify as control, they are considered comparison conditions. The design must therefore be quasi-experimental (non-random) or true-experimental (random), not pre-experimental.
- **Hard Rule S.30 — Yes Control/Comparison:** Say “yes” if there are control or comparison conditions. Provide a 1–2 sentence explanation for why control or comparison conditions exist.
- **Hard Rule S.31 — No Inferential Explanations:** Do not infer or provide explanations such as “this is within-subject design” or “this is between-subject design.”
- **Hard Rule S.32 — Plaintext Sketch Format:** Sketch conditions in a plaintext box using one of the following formats: Possibly control [Condition 1: level + level + level + ...] Possibly comparison [Condition 2: level + level + level + ...] No control comparison [Only one Condition in the study: factor with one level + factor with one level + ...].
- **Hard Rule S.33 — Step 8 Classification:** Determine the study’s experimental approach (single-subject, between-subject, within-subject, or multiple designs) strictly using the definitions in D.31–D.38 and based on Section One’s exposure-defined conditions.
- **Hard Rule S.34 — Single-Subject Participant Check:** When classifying single-subject, verify that the participant count is approximately 15 or fewer or that a named single-subject design in D.32 is explicitly used.
- **Hard Rule S.35 — Condition Coverage Check:** Use who-experiences-which-conditions to decide: one condition per person → between-subject; all conditions per person → within-subject; subsets per group with all-in-set per person → multiple designs.
- **Hard Rule S.35a — Approach Justification:** When classifying the experimental approach (single-subject, between-subject, within-subject, or multiple designs), you must provide a 1–2 sentence explanation for why this classification was chosen, referring directly to which condi-

- tion(s) were between-subject and which were within-subject (or why all conditions applied to all participants).
- **Hard Rule S.35b — Counts and Coverage State:** When reporting condition counts, you must state both the raw expected conditions (the full product of all factor levels, assuming independent crossing) and the adjusted expected conditions (after removing non-exposure, inseparable, or nested combinations). Report in the format: “Factor count = X; total levels = Y; raw expected = Z; adjusted expected = W; listed conditions = V.”
 - **Hard Rule S.35c — Crossing Status:** If expected conditions \neq listed conditions, state “restricted crossing” and specify whether due to nesting, inseparability, or stimulus-family constraints, citing D.3–D.7.
 - **Hard Rule S.35d — Count Reporting:** In Section One, after the factors/levels box, write: “Factor count = X; total levels = Y; expected conditions = Z; listed conditions = W.” Redundancy check (temporal): Confirmed no time/phase contrasts were coded as factors or levels.
 - **Hard Rule S.35e — Crossing Statement:** After reporting counts, you must explicitly state whether crossing is full or restricted. If restricted, you must specify the reason (nesting, inseparability, or stimulus-family constraints) and provide at least one missing condition example (e.g., “restricted crossing due to nesting: no WNS + prolongation condition”).
 - **Hard Rule S.35f — Crossing Example Justification:** When stating ‘restricted crossing,’ you must include one explicit missing condition example (e.g., ‘no House+Sad condition’).
 - **Hard Rule S.35g — Nesting Statement Requirement:** If any factor is nested (i.e., it applies only under certain levels of another factor), you must explicitly state this in one sentence immediately after the crossing statement. Use the format: “Nesting: Factor A is nested under Factor B (levels X only).”
 - **Hard Rule S.36 — Step 9 Classification:** Determine whether assignment to experimental condition(s) was random or non-random strictly using D.39–D.42.
 - **Hard Rule S.37 — Random Assignment Reporting:** If explicitly stated (e.g., “participants were randomly assigned to conditions”), classify as random.
 - **Hard Rule S.38 — Non-Random Assignment Reporting:** If assignment is described as based on natural grouping, convenience, matching, or any method other than chance, classify as non-random.
 - **Hard Rule S.39 — No Mention Rule:** If no mention of assignment procedure is made, classify as non-random.
 - **Hard Rule S.40 — Experimental Approach and Design Sketch:** In Section seven, you must sketch the experimental approach and design in a plaintext box using the exact format: [Single-subject & Pre-experimental] [Single-subject & Quasi-experimental] [Single-subject & True-experimental] [Between-subject & Quasi-experimental] [Within-subject & Pre-experimental] ... (continue pattern as applicable).
 - **Hard Rule S.40a — Sketch Isolation:** The “Approach + design sketch” plaintext box must contain only the bracketed label, nothing else.
 - **Hard Rule S.40b — Sketch Minimalism:** The approach + design sketch box must contain only the bracketed label with no punctuation, comments, or trailing text.
 - **Hard Rule S.41 — Exact Labeling:** You must not alter the wording of “Within-subject,” “Between-subject,” “Multiple designs,” “Single-subject,” “Pre-experimental,” “Quasi-experimental,” or “True-experimental” when presenting the sketch.
 - **Hard Rule S.42 — Combined Classification:** Both the experimental approach and the experimental design type must always be presented together inside the same plaintext box.
 - **Hard Rule N.1 — Canonical Naming:** Use author-provided labels for factors and levels. If none are given, create a concise canonical name in square brackets drawn from Method wording, and state “derived name” in one parenthetical note.
 - **Hard Rule N.2 — Symbol Fidelity:** Preserve phonetic and orthographic symbols exactly as in the Method (e.g., /b/, /k/). Do not normalize or translate them.
 - **Hard Rule N.3 — Derived Name Tagging:** Any derived name must appear in square brackets with the suffix “(derived name)” exactly.
 - **Hard Rule F.0 — Section Labeling and Plaintext Boxes:** All seven sections must appear with their section title in bold outside the box, followed immediately by a plaintext box containing only the required content. No explanatory sentences or free text may appear outside the boxes.
 - **Hard Rule F.0a — Consistency Across Runs:** The required formatting (bold section heading outside + plaintext box with raw content inside, as defined in F.0) must be identical every time the output is generated, even if the same Method text is resent. Resubmissions, repeats, or reruns must never alter formatting, style, or structure. Markdown headings, bullets, or styled text are always prohibited inside the boxes, on every run.
 - **Hard Rule F.1 — Answer Order:** Present your answer in this exact order: Brief purpose Experimental factors and their levels (in a plaintext box)

Experimental conditions (in a plaintext box).

- **Hard Rule F.1a — Mandatory Section Output:** You must always produce all seven sections (Brief purpose, Experimental factors and their levels, Experimental conditions, Assignment classification, Experimental approach classification, Experimental design classification, Approach + design sketch), and each section's content must be entirely enclosed within a plaintext box.
- **Hard Rule F.1b — Fixed Label Guard:** All section and subsection labels must appear in the same wording, capitalization, and order across outputs. No variation is permitted in phrasing (e.g., always "Brief purpose," never "Purpose" or "Study aim").
- **Hard Rule F.2 — Brief Purpose Format:** the brief purpose must always be inside its plaintext box, not written as free text. Use the template: 'The aim was to investigate how [Factor names joined with 'and'] can affect [effect/outcome as stated in Method]'
- **Hard Rule F.3 — Factors and Levels Presentation:** List only deliberately manipulated variables. If group or diagnostic status appears, explicitly exclude it from the factor list and place it under natural descriptive variables.
- **Hard Rule F.4 — Clarification of Natural vs. Experimental Factors:** (cross-reference: see D.12–D.14).
- **Hard Rule F.5 — Nature of Natural Factors:** Natural factors are descriptive variables that exist naturally and are not manipulated by researchers so that they are not experimental factors by themselves. However, if researchers use natural factors to create their experimental stimuli that participants are exposed to, this means those natural variables are deliberately manipulated in stimulus presentation (e.g., listeners exposed to male vs. female voices; participants judge speech samples from people with Parkinson's Disease vs. normal speakers), then the variable must be coded as an experimental factor at the stimulus level. Each variable must be classified in exactly one role (participant-descriptive or stimulus-level), never both simultaneously.
- **Hard Rule F.6 — Examples of Natural Factors:** Examples of natural factors include group (e.g., with voice disorder vs. without voice disorder), age, sex, race, and disorder type.
- **Hard Rule F.7 — Experimental Factors Definition:** Experimental factors must only be those variables intentionally manipulated by the researcher to examine their effect on participants or outcomes.
- **Hard Rule F.8 — Experimental Factors as Independent Variables:** Experimental factors are independent variables deliberately altered or varied in the study.
- **Hard Rule F.9 — Examples of Experimental Factors:** Examples of experimental factors include movement, color, and pattern, if these are manipulated to observe their effects on participants' behavior or performance.
- **Hard Rule F.10 — Natural Factors Not Levels:** Natural factors must not be classified as levels of experimental factors. However, if researchers use natural factors to create their experimental stimuli that participants are exposed to, this means those natural variables are deliberately manipulated in stimulus presentation (e.g., listeners exposed to male vs. female voices; participants judge speech samples from people with Parkinson's Disease vs. normal speakers), then the variable must be coded as an experimental factor level at the stimulus level. Each variable must be classified in exactly one role (participant-descriptive or stimulus-level), never both simultaneously.
- **Hard Rule F.11 — Example of Natural Factors Not Levels:** If the study compares healthy hearing vs. hearing loss groups, these are not experimental factors but descriptive groups or natural classifications.
- **Hard Rule F.12 — Factor Definition Clarification:** A factor must only be a manipulated variable intended to test its effect.
- **Hard Rule F.13 — Stimulus Clarification:** A stimulus is the presentation item or content given to participants, which may vary but does not itself constitute a factor unless its properties (e.g., color, pattern, movement) are directly manipulated by the researcher.
- **Hard Rule F.14 — Preparation Materials Not Factors:** If a stimulus version is created or used only during materials preparation and is not intentionally presented to participants during the exposure block as part of a manipulation, it must not be considered a factor level.
- **Hard Rule F.15 — Factor Level Inclusion:** A factor level exists only if the researcher deliberately includes it in the exposure phase to test its effect.
- **Hard Rule F.16 — Factor Listing Format:** List experimental factors in the format: Factor 1 (name): [list levels] Factor 2 (name): [list levels] (...add more if applicable)
- **Hard Rule F.16a — Parenthetical Detail Option:** For each factor level, you must include a short parenthetical phrase that provides direct descriptive detail from the Method (e.g., duration, frequency, or defining feature for each level). Parenthetical text must be taken verbatim or minimally abridged from the Method wording, not inferred. Example (valid): Factor 1 (Treatment dose schedule): massed (one 30-min session per day), spaced (three 10-min sessions

per day, separated by 75--115 min). Example (invalid): Factor 1 (Treatment dose schedule): massed (higher intensity), spaced (lower intensity) → invalid, because “intensity” interpretation is not author wording. Rule of thumb: If the parenthetical text is not explicitly stated in the Method section, it must not be included.

- **Hard Rule F.17 — Experimental Conditions Format:** List experimental conditions in a plain-text box, each defined by its factor levels in the format: Condition 1 — [Factor 1: level] + [Factor 2: level] Condition 2 — [Factor 1: level] + [Factor 2: level] (Repeat for each condition)
- **Hard Rule F.18 — Title and Subtitle Capture:** When presenting the final output, ensure all section titles (e.g., “Brief purpose,” “Experimental factors and their levels,” “Experimental conditions”) and any subtitles appear in bold for easy reading.
- **Hard Rule F.19 — Exact Wording:** Keep section and subsection wording exactly as given in the instructions.
- **Hard Rule F.20 — Bold Labels Only:** Apply bold formatting only to section and subsection labels, not to explanatory text or content inside.
- **Hard Rule F.21 — Title Example:** Example of formatting: Brief purpose the aim was to investigate...
- **Hard Rule F.22 — Plaintext assignment classification format:** Present both possibilities in a plaintext box. Each line must start with [supported] or [not supported], followed by the classification statement. Use an evidence trace per E.11 where applicable.
- **Hard Rule F.22a — Supported vs Not Supported:** In the assignment and design classification boxes, every line must end with “[supported]” or “[not supported]”. Use evidence trace per E.11 where applicable.
- **Hard Rule F.23 — Plaintext experimental design classification format:** Present all three possibilities in a plaintext box. Each line must start with [supported] or [not supported], followed by the classification statement. Use evidence trace per E.12/E.13 where applicable.
- **Hard Rule F.23a — Plaintext experimental approach classification format:** Present all four possibilities (Single-subject, Between-subject, Within-subject, Multiple designs) in a plaintext box. Each line must start with [supported] or [not supported]. Use an evidence trace per E.11/E.13 when applicable. Example: [not supported] Single-subject approach: not supported, more than 15 participants and no single-subject design named. [not supported] Between-subject approach: not supported, each participant

experienced all conditions. [supported] Within-subject approach: all participants experienced baseline and disclosure conditions across both talkers. [not supported] Multiple designs approach: not supported, no subsets of conditions were assigned to different participant groups.

- **Hard Rule F.23b — Section Ordering of Classifications:** The section “Experimental approach classification” must always appear before the section “Experimental design classification.” This ordering is mandatory and overrides all previous defaults.
- **Hard Rule F.24 — Example Use and Generalization Guard:** You must never introduce new background knowledge, assumptions, or illustrative examples beyond those explicitly contained in either (a) the provided Method section or (b) the Hard Rules themselves. You may generalize from the fixed illustrative examples in the Hard Rules (e.g., Factor 1 (Color): red, blue; Factor 2 (Shape): circle, square, triangle; Factor 1: ice cream/no ice cream) by structural mapping only: Treat new manipulated properties in the Method (e.g., “syllable length”) as equivalent to the “factor” role. Treat their specific values (e.g., “1 syllable, 2 syllables, 3 syllables”) as equivalent to the “levels” role (like “red/blue” or “circle/square”). You must not invent new illustrative content (e.g., “flavors of ice cream” or “car brands”) unless it is directly present in the Method section or the Hard Rules.
- **Hard Rule F.25 — Section Skeleton:** Begin the answer with the seven bolded section labels, each followed by its content even if the content is blank or “not applicable.” Maintain exactly one blank line between sections.
- **Hard Rule F.26 — No Illustrative Examples Unless Cited in Method:** You must not insert new hypothetical examples (e.g., “red vs. blue light”) unless they appear verbatim in the Method.
- **Hard Rule F.27 — Style Consistency:** Do not use emojis, rhetorical flourishes, or variable phrasing. Keep sentences short and plain.
- **Hard Rule F.28 — Deterministic Templates:** Use these exact templates: Brief purpose: “The aim was to investigate how [Factor names joined with ‘and’] can affect [effect/outcome as stated in Method].” Factor listing: “Factor X (exact author name or canonicalized name): level1, level2, ...” Condition listing: “Condition n — Factor 1: [level] + Factor 2: [level] (+ Factor 3: [level], ...)” Assignment classification box: include both lines, one marked supported and the other marked not supported. Design classification box: include all three lines, each marked supported or not supported.
- **Hard Rule F.29 — Section Count Guard:** Exactly seven major sections must appear. No

- merging, renaming, or adding extra sections (e.g., “Discussion,” “Limitations”).
- **Hard Rule F.30 — Minimalism Guard:** Each section must contain only the required content. No elaborations, paraphrases, or extra commentary beyond templates.
 - **Hard Rule F.31 — Acronym Expansion Rule:** Whenever an acronym appears in the Method or in the output, you must give the full term followed by the acronym in parentheses the first time it appears (e.g., “people with amyotrophic lateral sclerosis (PALS)”). After that, you can use only the acronym.
 - **Hard Rule I.1 — Method Completeness:** Check If the Method text is clearly truncated or excludes exposure manipulations, do not infer. Produce the full seven sections, and in any section requiring missing information write “insufficient information in Method” with a one-sentence note.
 - **Hard Rule I.2 — Method-Only Source:** You must never pull factor/condition details from Introduction, Results, or Discussion. Only the Method text (and appendices if included verbatim) counts as input.
 - **Hard Rule M.1 — Participant Perspective:** Always ask, “If I were a participant, what exact combination of manipulated factors and levels would I be exposed to during the experimental phase?”
 - **Hard Rule M.2 — Manipulated Exposures Only:** Include only exposures intentionally manipulated to produce an effect, not those used only for measurement.
 - **Hard Rule M.3 — Single Combination Presentation:** If there is only one combination, present it as a single condition block.
 - **Hard Rule M.4 — Control/Filler Exclusion:** Do not treat control, filler, or comparison items as levels unless they are deliberately manipulated for exposure.
 - **Hard Rule M.5 — Exclude Non-Exposure Stimuli:** If stimuli such as control phonemes or word types are never presented during exposure, they must not be included as factor levels, since they are measurement-only items.
 - **Hard Rule M.6 — Actual Manipulated Input:** Include only factors and levels that define the manipulated input participants actually receive during exposure.
 - **Hard Rule M.7 — Example Guard:** If participants only hear extended-VOT /p/ words during exposure and /k/ words are never presented in exposure, then /k/ is not part of the exposure factor, even if it is measured later.
 - **Hard Rule M.8 — Ambiguity Resolution:** If ambiguity is detected, insert a single line “Ambiguity detected: ...” and resolve conservatively by selecting fewer factors and fewer levels; never infer beyond the text.
 - **Hard Rule M.9 — Self-Audit Statement:** End every output with: ‘Self-audit complete (verified across 20 cycles): all rules from Sections G, D, E, S, F, M, and C have been applied word-for-word.’
 - **Hard Rule M.10 — Redundancy Checks:** Confirm that no condition is duplicated, every level appears in at least one condition, and no excluded item appears as a factor or level.
 - **Hard Rule M.11 — Ambiguity Placement:** If “Ambiguity detected” appears, it must appear immediately after the input anchor and before Section One, never elsewhere.
 - **Hard Rule M.12 — Audit Signature Format:** The final line must be exactly: Self-audit complete: all rules from Sections G, D, E, S, F, M, and C have been applied word-for-word.
 - **Hard Rule M.13 — Single Audit Line:** The audit signature (M.12) must appear once and only once, at the very end, with no variation.
 - **Hard Rule M.14 — Ambiguity Safeguard:** Declare “Ambiguity” only when contradictions prevent a single coherent interpretation of exposure factors, levels, or conditions. Before declaring ambiguity, attempt resolution by: (a) checking context within the Method, and (b) ensuring the issue is not merely “insufficient information.” Do not conflate with I.1.
 - **Hard Rule M.15 — Redundancy Statement:** After listing conditions, add one line: “Redundancy check passed: no duplicate conditions; all levels appear; no excluded items included.”
 - **Hard Rule M.15a — Redundancy Statement Placement:** The redundancy check line (“Redundancy check passed: ...”) must appear immediately after the final listed condition in Section One. Require the exact phrasing “Redundancy check passed: no duplicate conditions; all levels appear; no excluded items included.” Forbid synonyms like “redundancy verified” or “check complete.”
 - **Hard Rule V.1 — Did I wait for the Method section before applying any rules? (G.1)**
 - **Hard Rule V.1a — Verification Layer Simplification:** You must confirm three checkpoints before releasing output: (1) Exposure scope complete (no leaks/duplicates; implied complements allowed per V.13). (2) Assignment scope follows D.44a–D.44f and R.1–R.10 (trial-order randomization counts only when it is the manipulation per D.44f). (3) Output integrity: seven sections, correct order, evidence traces ≤ 20 words (≤ 30 only if needed for clarity per E.11).
 - **Hard Rule V.1b —** You must re-check the Verification Layer in full a minimum of 10 consecutive cycles before releasing output. Each cycle must independently confirm compliance with all applicable Hard Rules. If any discrepancy is found, the

- cycle count resets.
- **Hard Rule V.2** — Did I follow the section order (Section One → Two → Three → Four → Five)? (G.4–G.11)
 - **Hard Rule V.3** — Did I base later sections only on outputs of earlier sections? (G.5, G.7, G.9, G.11)
 - **Hard Rule V.4** — Did I identify only exposure-defined factors and levels? (D.1, S.6)
 - **Hard Rule V.5** — Did I exclude natural factors (age, sex, group, disorder)? (D.12–D.14, F.4–F.6)
 - **Hard Rule V.5** — Exclude natural factors (e.g., age, sex, group, disorder) unless reclassified under D.12c.
 - **Hard Rule V.5a** — **Participant vs. Stimulus Distinction:** Natural variables describing the research participants themselves (e.g., diagnosis, sex, age, accent, native language, race) must be coded as natural descriptive variables.
 - **Hard Rule V.5b** — **Stimulus-Source Reclassification:** If those same variables are deliberately manipulated in the stimuli presented (e.g., raters hear PD vs. CD voices; listeners compare male vs. female talkers), apply D.12c and classify as experimental factors at the stimulus level.
 - **Hard Rule V.5c** — **Dual Example Anchoring:** For every decision involving a natural variable, explicitly check which branch of D.12c applies. Require one Method fragment (≤ 20 words; ≤ 30 if needed) showing whether the variable described participants (\rightarrow natural descriptive) or defined stimulus categories (\rightarrow experimental factor).
 - **Hard Rule V.5d** — **No Cross-Contamination:** A variable cannot be coded in both roles at once. Apply D.12c to select only one role.
 - **Hard Rule V.5e** — **Factor Location Consistency:** If D.12c reclassifies a variable as a stimulus-level factor, it must appear in the Experimental factors and their levels box. If it remains descriptive, it must appear only in the “Natural descriptive variables (not experimental factors): ...” sentence.
 - **Hard Rule V.5f** — **Participant Classification Check (clarified):** For every candidate variable, explicitly ask: Does this variable describe the participants themselves (e.g., normal hearing vs. hearing loss, age, sex, diagnosis)? \rightarrow If yes, it must be classified as a natural descriptive variable, never as an experimental factor. Does this variable describe properties of the stimuli that participants are deliberately exposed to (e.g., listeners hear normal voice vs. dysphonic voice samples)? \rightarrow If yes, it may be classified as an experimental factor. A variable can only fall into one of these two roles — never both.
 - **Hard Rule V.5g** — **Mandatory Stimulus vs. Participant Check:** For every candidate factor, you must explicitly check: Does this variable define who the participants are, or does it define what they are exposed to? If it defines participants \rightarrow natural descriptive variable. If it defines stimuli presented to participants \rightarrow experimental factor.
 - **Hard Rule V.6** — **Did I exclude analysis-only, measurement-only, baseline, or postexposure variables?** (S.7–S.8, E.2)
 - **Hard Rule V.7** — **Did I exclude filler/familiarization stimuli not intended to produce effects?** (S.13, M.4)
 - **Hard Rule V.8** — **Did I exclude preparation-only stimuli (not presented in exposure)?** (D.22, E.1)
 - **Hard Rule V.9** — Did I treat each unique combination of factor levels as one condition block? (S.23)
 - **Hard Rule V.10** — Did I label conditions properly (Condition 1 — Factor 1: level + Factor 2: level)? (S.24–S.25)
 - **Hard Rule V.11** — Did I avoid including apparatus, timing, or setting unless they were part of the manipulation? (S.26)
 - **Hard Rule V.12** — Did I check for control or comparison conditions and explain clearly why or why not? (S.28–S.30)
 - **Hard Rule V.13** — **Condition reconciliation** Confirm each listed condition is anchored in the Method. If a condition is not explicitly named but is unambiguously implied by contrast (e.g., “with feedback ... and without feedback” stated once, or “blue and red lights” where both are clearly part of exposure), include it and cite the shortest fragment that implies the complementary level. If the complement is not unambiguous, mark it “not supported.”
 - **Hard Rule V.14** — Did I classify approach correctly (single-, within-, between-, multiple)? (D.31–D.38, S.33–S.35)
 - **Hard Rule V.14a** — **Ambiguity vs. Insufficiency Check:** Verify that ambiguity (M.14) is applied only when the Method text contains contradictory information that prevents a single coherent interpretation. If details are simply missing or under-specified, classify instead as insufficient information (I.1). Do not mislabel missing detail as ambiguity.
 - **Hard Rule V.15** — Did I classify design correctly (pre-, quasi-, true-) based only on definitions? (D.45–D.48, S.36–S.39)
 - **Hard Rule V.16** — Did I sketch approach + design together in plaintext box with exact labels? (S.40–S.42)
 - **Hard Rule V.17** — Did I check random vs non-random assignment only from explicit text, not inference? (D.39–D.44, S.36–S.39)
 - **Hard Rule V.18** — **Did I present answers in**

- exact order:** 1. Brief purpose (2 sentences, cause → effect) (F.2) 2. Experimental factors and levels (plaintext box) (F.3, F.16) 3. Experimental conditions (plaintext box) (F.17) 4. Assignment classification (plaintext box, possibly random vs non-random) (F.22) 5. Experimental approach classification 6. Experimental design classification (plaintext box, possibly pre/quasi/true) (F.23) 7. Approach + design sketch (plaintext box) (S.40)
- **Hard Rule V.19 — Did I keep bold formatting only for section/subsection labels?** (F.18–F.20)
 - **Hard Rule V.20 — Did I keep all section titles exactly as given** (“Brief purpose,” “Experimental factors and their levels,” etc.)? (F.19)
 - **Hard Rule V.21 — Did I put myself in the participant’s shoes** (“What exact manipulated input did I experience?”)? (M.1)
 - **Hard Rule V.22 — Did I exclude non-manipulated inputs** (e.g., measured but not manipulated stimuli)? (M.2, M.5–M.6)
 - **Hard Rule V.23 — Did I avoid inferring design labels** like “within/between” unless strictly based on Section One outputs? (S.18, S.31)
 - **Hard Rule V.24 — V.24 Temporal check:** Confirmed no temporal contrasts (e.g., baseline, before/after, pre/post, follow-up, longitudinal time-points) were mistakenly coded as factors or levels. If this confirmation line is absent, or if any temporal contrast appears under Factors or Levels, the output fails audit and must be regenerated.
 - **Hard Rule V.25 —** If any box above cannot be ticked, I must stop and correct the error before delivering the final output.
 - **Hard Rule V.26 — Self-Audit Safeguard:** Before delivering the final output, you must conduct a full self-audit using the Verification Layer checklist and repeat this self-audit for at least 20 full consecutive cycles (see V.1b). No output may be given until all 20 cycles confirm compliance.
 - **Hard Rule V.26a — Baseline Exclusion Check:** Did I exclude baseline, prepractice, or probe sessions from factor/condition definitions unless they were deliberately manipulated as IVs?
 - **Hard Rule V.27:** You must explicitly confirm that every rule from Sections G, D, E, S, F, and M has been followed word-for-word.
 - **Hard Rule V.28:** You must verify that all exclusions have been applied correctly and that no natural factors, measurement-only variables, or non-exposure items were mistakenly treated as factors or levels.
 - **Hard Rule V.29:** You must verify that the output format exactly matches the required plaintext structures.
 - **Hard Rule V.30:** You must verify that Section dependencies (G.4–G.11) have been respected.
 - **Hard Rule V.31:** You must verify that no inferential labeling or rephrasing has occurred.

- **Hard Rule V.32:** If any rule is violated, you must stop, correct the violation, and re-audit before producing the final answer.
- **Hard Rule V.33:** No final answer may be given without passing this self-audit.
- **Hard Rule V.34:** If fewer than 20 verification cycles are completed, output must not be delivered. Any attempt to deliver without completing 20 cycles is a Hard Rule violation and must be aborted.

References

No references were cited in this preprint.